

1 ***Pseudomonas soli* sp. nov., a novel producer of xantholysin congeners**

2

3 Javier Pascual, Marina García-López, Cristina Carmona, Thiciana da S. Sousa, Nuria de Pedro,
4 Bastien Cautain, Jesús Martín, Francisca Vicente, Fernando Reyes, Gerald F. Bills^a, Olga
5 Genilloud*.

6

7 Fundación MEDINA, Avenida del Conocimiento, 3. Parque Tecnológico de Ciencias de la
8 Salud. E-18016 Granada (Spain).

9

10 ^aCurrent address: Texas Therapeutics Institute, The Brown Foundation Institute of Molecular
11 Medicine, The University of Texas Health Science Center, 1881 East Road, 3SCR6.4676,
12 Houston, TX 77054, USA.

13

14 Running title: *Pseudomonas soli* sp. nov.

15

16 *Corresponding author at: Fundación MEDINA, Avenida del Conocimiento, 3. Parque
17 Tecnológico de Ciencias de la Salud. E-18016 Granada (Spain). Phone: + 34 958 993 965
18 E-mail: olga.genilloud@medinaandalucia.es

19

20 Abbreviations: DSS, diffusion sandwich system; FAMES, fatty acids methyl esters; HIF,
21 hypoxia-inducible-factor; LC-HRMS, liquid chromatography-high resolution mass
22 spectrometry; ML, maximum likelihood; MLSA, multilocus sequence analysis; MP, maximum
23 parsimony; NJ, neighbor joining; SBS, society for biomolecular sciences; VHL, Von Hippel-
24 Lindau syndrome.

25

26 The GenBank/ EMBL/ DDBJ accession number for the 16S rRNA, *gyrB*, *rpoB* and *rpoD* gene
27 sequences of strain F-279,208^T are HF930598, HF930595, HF930596, HF930597, respectively.

28

29

30 ABSTRACT

31 A chemoorganotrophic Gram-negative bacterium was isolated by means of a diffusion sandwich
32 system from a soil sample from the Sierra Nevada National Park, Spain. Strain F-279,208^T was
33 oxidase and catalase positive, strictly aerobic, non-spore-forming and motile by single polar
34 flagellum. Phylogenetic analysis of the 16S rRNA, *gyrB*, *rpoB* and *rpoD* genes revealed that
35 strain F-279,208^T belongs to the *Pseudomonas putida* group with *P. mosselii* and *P.*
36 *entomophila* as its closest relatives. DNA-DNA hybridization assays and phenotypic traits
37 confirmed that this strain belongs to a novel species of the genus *Pseudomonas*, for which the
38 name *Pseudomonas soli* sp. nov. is proposed. The type strain is F-279,208^T (=DSM 28043^T
39 =LMG 27941^T), and during fermentation it produces xantholysins, a family of
40 lipodepsipeptides. The major compound, xantholysin A, showed an interesting activity in a
41 RCC4 kidney tumor cell line with inactivation of VHL linked with the HIF pathway, without
42 any cytotoxic effects against other human tumor cell lines tested including, liver, pancreas and
43 breast.

44
45 **Keywords:** *Pseudomonas soli* sp. nov.; Diffusion sandwich system, Sierra Nevada National
46 Park, Multilocus Sequence Analysis, cytotoxic activity, HIF pathway, lipodepsipeptide,
47 xantholysin.

48
49 **Scope of the paper:** Systematics

50

51

52 Introduction

53 The genus *Pseudomonas* has had an important role in the biotechnology and pharmaceutical
54 industries due to its metabolic versatility [4]. Since 1889, when Bouchard observed that the
55 injection of small quantities of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* cultures (earlier synonym *Bacillus*
56 *pyocyaneus*) prevented the development of anthrax in rabbits which had been previously
57 injected with a virulent culture of *B. anthracis* [5], the antibiotic and cytotoxic effects of
58 *Pseudomonas* strains have frequently been reported. The vast metabolic diversity of
59 *Pseudomonas* spp. is reflected on the production of a wide variety of bioactive molecules such
60 as mupirocin, fosfadecin, fosfocytosin or the recently described xantholysins, among others [1,
61 3, 4, 8]. The xantholysins are a family of lipodepsipeptides which include four congeners,
62 xantholysin A, the main compound produced with molecular mass 1775.4 Da, and minor
63 variants xantholysin B (1761.2 Da), xantholysin C (1802.0 Da) and xantholysin D (1775.2 Da)
64 [8]. Properties of the major compound xantholysin A, shared with several other *Pseudomonas*
65 lipopeptides, include antifungal activity and antibiotic activity against Gram-positive bacteria, a
66 supportive role in biofilm formation, and facilitation of surface colonization through swarming

67 [8]. Albeit Li and colleagues [8] predicted also an antiviral activity of the xantholysin A, to date
68 no cytotoxic activities in tumor cell lines are known to be produced by this compound.
69 During the course of a screening of bacterial soil strains for production of novel bioactive
70 compounds, extracts of a newly isolated strain, F-279,208^T, were identified as cytotoxic against
71 several human tumor cell lines. This strain was isolated from a soil sample collected from the
72 Sierra Nevada National Park, Granada, Spain (36° 55'26''N 3° 21'15''W) at an elevation of
73 1125 m, in May of 2011. A diffusion sandwich system (DSS) incubated in a soil-simulated
74 environment in the laboratory for 3 wk at 18 °C was used for the isolation. The DSS is an array
75 of 384 of miniature diffusion chambers arranged in standard SBS format. Its design was
76 inspired by the concept of the Ichip [12], and developed by our group as a tool to get access to
77 previously uncultured bacteria. Details of its design and proof of concept will be published in
78 the Environmental Microbiology journal.

79 Reference strains used in this taxonomic study were: *Pseudomonas entomophila* CECT 7985^T,
80 *Pseudomonas mosselii* DSM 17497^T, *Pseudomonas plecoglossicida* DSM 15088^T and
81 *Pseudomonas taiwanensis* DSM 21245^T. Strain F-279,208^T and reference strains were grown
82 aerobically on TSA or TSB for 48 h at 28 °C, for inocula or sample preparation. Data for
83 *Pseudomonas monteilii* BCRC 17520^T were taken from the bibliography.

84 Strain F-279,208^T was Gram negative according to a 3% KOH assay, oxidase- and catalase
85 positive based on the 1 % (w/v) *N,N,N',N'*-tetramethyl-*p*-phenylenediamine dihydrochloride and
86 3% (v/v) hydrogen peroxide solutions, respectively. It showed an aerobic metabolism, was able
87 to grow on TSA at 4-37 °C but not at 45 °C and on nutrient agar supplemented with 0-6% (w/v)
88 NaCl but not with 7%. Cells were rod-shaped (0.5-0.9 μm wide × 1.0-2.2 μm long), non-spore-
89 forming and motile by a single polar flagellum, as seen after flagella staining [6]
90 (Supplementary Fig. S1). After 48 h incubation at 28 °C on TSA plates, colonies showed a topaz
91 colour and were circular (approximately 1.2 mm in diam), convex with regular edges. A star
92 shaped precipitate appeared in the medium during the bacterial growth (Supplementary Fig. S2).
93 Strain F-279,208^T produced fluorescein, but not pyocyanin, on King B and King A media,
94 respectively [7].

95 Commercial miniaturized API 20E, API 20NE and API ZYM galleries (bioMérieux) and carbon
96 utilization test based on Biolog GN2 MicroPlates (MicroLog System) were utilized according to
97 the manufacturer's instructions. API 20E, API 20NE and Biolog GN2 plates were examined
98 after 48h and API ZYM after 4h of incubation. Miniaturized test results were recorded in
99 triplicate. Differential physiological and biochemical characteristics are shown in diagnostic
100 Table 1.

101 For FAMES analysis, fatty acids were extracted, saponified and methylated according to
102 standard protocols (MIDI Microbial Identification System) [16], and individual FAMES were
103 identified using the Microbial Identification System using the TSBA50 library (MIDI). The

104 major cellular fatty acids of the strain F-279,208^T were: summed feature C_{16:1}ω7c and/or iso-
105 C_{15:0} 2-OH (24.8%), C_{16:0} (23.7%), C_{18:1} ω7c (14.4%), and C_{10:0} 3-OH (12.4%) along with C_{17:0}
106 CYCLO, C_{12:0} 2-OH, C_{12:0} 3-OH, C_{12:1} 3-OH and C_{12:0} (Supplementary Table S1). Our isolate
107 shared similar FAMES profile with the other *Pseudomonas* spp. analyzed in this survey and this
108 was consistent with previously published results [10, 19], supporting its classification in the
109 genus *Pseudomonas* [18].

110 For fingerprinting, MLSA and hybridization DNA-DNA assays, genomic DNAs were extracted
111 with the DNeasy Blood & Tissue kit (Qiagen) and the concentration and purity of each sample
112 was determined.

113 Its genetic distinctness to other related type strains of the genus *Pseudomonas* was evaluated by
114 fingerprinting analysis based on the Rep PCR (GTG)₅ technique. The methods are detailed in
115 Supplementary Methods S1. The genomic fingerprinting pattern of strain F-279,208^T differed
116 from other related species (Supplementary Fig. S3), sharing a similarity of 69.6% and 65.2%
117 regarding to *P. entomophila* CECT 7985^T and *P. mosselii* DSM 17497^T. Albeit, as far as we
118 know, this approach has not been previously validated as a tool for the discrimination of
119 *Pseudomonas* species nor inferring their phylogenetic relationships, this result suggests that our
120 isolate has genetic differences with other species belonging to the *P. putida* phylogenetic group,
121 and then our isolate is not a clone of other type strains.

122 To determine the phylogenetic relationship of our isolate, near full-length 16S rRNA and partial
123 *gyrB*, *rpoB* and *rpoD* gene sequences were analysed, individually as well as concatenating its
124 sequences through a multilocus sequence analysis (MLSA). Material and methods for
125 amplification, sequencing and phylogenetic analyses are detailed in Supplementary Methods S2.

126 According to EzTaxon-e database, the closest relatives of strain F-279,208^T were *P. mosselii*
127 (AF072688), *P. entomophila* (AY907566), *P. plecoglossicida* (AB009457), *P. taiwanensis*
128 (EU103629) and *P. monteilii* (AF064458) sharing a similarity of 99.51%, 99.23%, 99.17%,
129 99.15% and 99.03%, respectively of the 16S rRNA gene sequence. This result agreed with the
130 pairwise nucleotide similarity values of 16S rRNA gene sequences obtained in this survey
131 (Supplementary Table S2). According to this result, our isolate is placed in the *P. putida*
132 phylogenetic clade [11]. The lengths of the fragments used for further phylogenetic analysis
133 ranged from 1414 to 1441 nt (16S rRNA gene), 900 to 915 nt (*rpoB*), 705 to 717 nt (*rpoD*), 705
134 to 708 nt (*gyrB*), and 3,736 to 3,778 nt (four concatenated genes). Supplementary Table S2
135 shows the pairwise sequence similarities (%) of each dataset. The different trees obtained with
136 the NJ, MP and ML methods are shown in Fig. 1 and Supplementary Figs. S4, S5 and S6.

137 Irrespective of the gene analysed and the tree reconstruction method applied, *P. soli* F-279,208^T
138 was always placed in a separate branch with the type strains of *P. mosselii* and *P. entomophila*
139 as its nearest neighbours, except for the trees based on the *rpoB* gene and calculated with the
140 NJ, MP and ML algorithms. The relative positions of the rest of the species belonging to the *P.*

141 *putida* phylogenetic group, *P. cremoricolorata*, *P. fulva*, *P. japonica*, *P. monteilii*, *P. parafulva*,
142 *P. plecoglossicida*, *P. putida*, *P. taiwanensis* and *P. vranovensis*, varied depending on the
143 clustering method (NJ, MP and ML) and the set of sequences used. Further, we checked these
144 genes to detect possible recombination events with the RDP4 Beta 4.16 program and did not
145 detect any signal of HGT in the sequences except for *rpoD*, where two possible recombination
146 events were detected. One of them was detected in the sequence of *P. plecoglossicida* (positions
147 from 200 to 298 in alignment) being the minor parent *P. fulva*, and the other in the sequence of
148 *P. taiwanensis* (positions from 283 to 326 in alignment) being in this case *P. japonica* the minor
149 parent. Despite this, the topologies of the trees taking into account or excluding both
150 hypothetical recombinant regions in the multiple alignment of the *rpoD* gene were not
151 statistically different between the resulting trees according to the Shimodaira-Hasegawa test
152 (data not shown). Therefore, the phylogenetic discrepancies among housekeeping genes were
153 most probably due to their different evolutionary rates.

154 Because multilocus sequence analysis (MLSA) uses a higher number of nucleotides than a
155 single gene analysis and avoids possible confounding effects of horizontal gene transfer on
156 phylogenetic relationships, MLSA is considered more likely to diagnose the correct
157 evolutionary pattern among the species [14, 15]. The highest interspecific sequence similarities
158 found between strain F-279,208^T and its phylogenetic neighbours were 99.5% (16S rRNA),
159 96.1% (*rpoB*), 91.6% (*rpoD*), 93.5% (*gyrB*) and 96.1% (MLSA of four genes concatenated) to
160 *P. mosselii* in all cases (Supplementary Table S2). These values were clearly lower than the
161 maximum interspecific similarity found among the rest of the *Pseudomonas* species analysed
162 99.8% (16S rRNA), 99.6% (*rpoB*), 92.4% (*rpoD*) and 94.5% (*gyrB*). The highest interspecific
163 sequence similarity found in the MLSA based on these four genes between strain F-279,208^T
164 and its phylogenetic neighbours (96.1%) was lower than the threshold value (97%) established
165 by Mulet and co-workers [9] for strains belonging to the same species in the genus
166 *Pseudomonas*. Consequently, strain F-279,208^T could not be assigned phylogenetically to any
167 species with names with standing in nomenclature.

168 DNA-DNA hybridizations between strain F-279,208^T and its closest phylogenetic relative *P.*
169 *mosselii* DSM 17497^T were measured according to Ziemke et al. [21] and Urdiain et al. [17].
170 The hybridization temperature was 70 °C. The average value obtained was 55.3±3.4% (in
171 triplicate). This value was clearly lower than the accepted species threshold for species
172 delineation of 70% [20], and therefore established that strain F-279,208^T belonged to a unique
173 species.

174 When grown in Kido medium (Supplementary Methods S3) for three days in an orbital shaker
175 (220 rpm) at 18 °C, strain F-279,208^T produced xantholysins A-D [8], as confirmed by the
176 presence in the LC-HRMS analysis of the extract of pseudomolecular ions ([M+H]⁺) at *m/z*
177 1776.0902, 1762.0731, 1802.1080, and 1776.0906, respectively (Supplementary Fig S7).

178 Additionally, a fifth minor peak having the same molecular weight as xantholysin B was also
179 detected during this analysis. Once isolated (Supplementary Methods S3), the major compound
180 (xantholysin A) showed an interesting activity in RCC4 kidney tumor cell line who present an
181 inactivating mutation of the VHL gene (Supplementary Fig S8) linked with activation of the
182 HIF pathway [2]. More interestingly, it did not cause cytotoxic effects against other human
183 tumor cell lines including, liver, pancreas and breast tumor cell lines (Supplementary Methods
184 S4 and Supplementary Table S3).

185 Collectively comparing the morphologic, metabolic, physiologic, chemotaxonomic,
186 phylogenetic and genetic proprieties of strain F-279,208^T with those of its closest phylogenetic
187 neighbours, we concluded that this strain represented a new isolate of a new species belonging
188 to the *P. putida* group into the genus *Pseudomonas*, for which we propose the name
189 *Pseudomonas soli* sp. nov.

190

191 **Description of *Pseudomonas soli* sp. nov.**

192 *Pseudomonas soli* sp. nov. (so'li. L. neut. gen. n. soli of soil, the source of the type strain).

193 Cells are Gram-negative rods, 0.5-0.9 μm wide and 1.0-2.2 μm long, non-spore-forming, motile
194 by single polar flagellum. Chemoorganotrophic, aerobic, oxidase and catalase positive. After
195 48h incubation at 28 °C on TSA, colonies are topaz in colour, circular, convex with regular
196 edges. A star-shaped precipitate appears inside the medium during bacterial growth. Fluorescein
197 pigment is produced, but pyocyanin is not. Growth is observed at 4-37 °C and in the presence of
198 0-6% (w/v) NaCl. Other phenotypic characteristics are given in diagnostic Table 1. The most
199 abundant FAMES are: summed feature C_{16:1}ω7c and/or iso-C_{15:0} 2-OH, C_{16:0}, C_{18:1} ω7c, and C_{10:0}
200 3-OH.

201 The type strain is F-279,208^T (=DSM 28043^T =LMG 27941^T), isolated by a Diffusion Sandwich
202 System from a soil sample taken from The Sierra Nevada National Park (Spain).

203

204 **Acknowledgments**

205

206 This research was supported by the Non-Oriented Basic Research Program of the Spanish
207 Ministry of Science (Project SAF2010-15010). The authors thank Professor Dr. J. P. Euzéby for
208 his advice on the nomenclature of the novel species *Pseudomonas soli* sp. nov. We are grateful
209 to the administration of The Sierra Nevada National Park for permission to collect soils.

210

211 **References**

- 212 [1] Buckingham, J. (2011) Dictionary of Natural Products on DVD, CRC Press, Boca Raton,
213 USA.
- 214 [2] Chan D.A., Giaccia A.J. (2008) Targeting cancer cells by synthetic lethality: autophagy and
215 VHL in cancer therapeutics. *Cell Cycle* 7, 2987-2990.
- 216 [3] Fuller, A.T., Mellows, G., Woolford, M., Banks, G.T., Barrow, K.D., Chain, E.D. (1971)
217 Pseudomonic acid: an antibiotic produced by *Pseudomonas fluorescens*. *Nature* 234, 416-
218 417.
- 219 [4] Gross, H. and Loper, J.E. (2009) Genomics of secondary metabolite production by
220 *Pseudomonas* spp. *Nat. Prod. Rep.* 26, 1408-1446.
- 221 [5] Hays, E.E., Wells, I.C., Katzman, P.A., Cain, C.K., Jacobs, F.A., Thayer, S.A., Doisy, E.A.,
222 Gaby, W.L., Roberts, E.C., Muir, R.D., Carroll, C.J., Jones, L.R., Wade, N.J. (1945)
223 Antibiotic substances produced by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. *J. Biol. Chem.* 159, 725-750.
- 224 [6] Heimbrook, M.E., Wang, W.L., Campbell, G. (1989) Staining bacterial flagella easily. *J.*
225 *Clin. Microbiol.* 27, 2612-2615.
- 226 [7] King E.O., Ward M.K., Raney D.E. (1954) Two simple media for the demonstration of
227 pyocyanin and fluorescin. *J. Lab. Clin. Med.* 44, 301-307.
- 228 [8] Li W., Rokni-Zadeh H., De Vleeschouwer M., Ghequire M.G., Sinnaeve D., Xie G.L.,
229 Rozenski J., Madder A., Martins J.C., De Mot R. (2013) The antimicrobial compound
230 xantholysin defines a new group of *Pseudomonas* cyclic lipopeptides. *PLoS One.* 8,
231 e62946.
- 232 [9] Mulet, M., Lalucat, J., García-Valdés, E. (2010) DNA sequence-based analysis of the
233 *Pseudomonas* species. *Environ. Microbiol.* 12, 1513-1530.
- 234 [10] Mulet, M., Gomila, M., Lemaitre, B., Lalucat, J., Garcia-Valdes, E. (2012) Taxonomic
235 characterisation of *Pseudomonas* strain L48 and formal proposal of *Pseudomonas*
236 *entomophila* sp. nov. *Syst. Appl. Microbiol.* 35, 145-149.
- 237 [11] Mulet, M., Gomila, M., Scotta, C., Sánchez, D., Lalucat, J., García-Valdés, E. (2012)
238 Concordance between whole-cell matrix-assisted laser-desorption/ionization time-of-flight
239 mass spectrometry and multilocus sequence analysis approaches in species discrimination
240 within the genus *Pseudomonas*. *Syst. Appl. Microbiol.* 35, 455-464.
- 241 [12] Nichols D., Cahoon N., Trakhtenberg E.M., Pham L., Mehta A., Belanger A., Kanigan T.,
242 Lewis K., Epstein S.S. (2010) Use of ichip for high-throughput in situ cultivation of
243 "uncultivable" microbial species. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 76, 2445-2450.
- 244 [13] Nishimori E., Kita-Tsukamoto K., Wakabayashi H. (2000) *Pseudomonas plecoglossicida*
245 sp. nov., the causative agent of bacterial haemorrhagic ascites of ayu, *Plecoglossus*
246 *altivelis*. *Int. J. Syst. Evol. Microbiol.* 50, 83-89.

- 247 [14] Pascual, J., Macián, M.C., Arahal, D.R., Garay, E., Pujalte, M.J. (2010) Multilocus
248 sequence analysis of the central clade of the genus *Vibrio* by using the 16S rRNA, *recA*,
249 *pyrH*, *rpoD*, *gyrB*, *rctB* and *toxR* genes. Int. J. Syst. Evol. Microbiol. 60, 154-165.
- 250 [15] Pascual, J., Lucena T., Ruvira, M.A., Giordano, A., Gambacorta, A., Garay, E., Arahal,
251 D.R., Pujalte, M.J., Macián, M.C. (2011) *Pseudomonas litoralis* sp. nov., isolated from
252 Mediterranean seawater. Int. J. Syst. Evol. Microbiol. 62, 438-444.
- 253 [16] Sasser, M. (1990) Identification of bacteria by gas chromatography of cellular fatty acids,
254 MIDI Technical Note 101. Newark, DE: MIDI, Inc.
- 255 [17] Urdiain, M., López-López, A., Gonzalo, C., Büsse, H.J., Langer, S., Kämpfer, P., Rosselló-
256 Mora, R. (2008) Reclassification of *Rhodobium marinum* and *Rhodobium pfennigii* as
257 *Afifella marina* gen. nov. comb. nov. and *Afifella pfennigii* comb. nov., a new genus of
258 photoheterotrophic Alphaproteobacteria and emended descriptions of *Rhodobium*,
259 *Rhodobium orientis* and *Rhodobium gokarnense*. Syst. Appl. Microbiol. 31, 339-351.
- 260 [18] Vancanneyt, M., Witt, S., Abraham, W.R., Kersters, K., Fredrickson, H.L. (1996) Fatty
261 acid content in whole-cell hydrolysates and phospholipid fractions of pseudomonads: a
262 taxonomic evaluation. Syst. Appl. Microbiol. 19, 528-540.
- 263 [19] Wang, L.T., Tai, C.J., Wu, Y.C., Chen, Y.B., Lee, F.L., Wang, S.L. (2010) *Pseudomonas*
264 *taiwanensis* sp. nov., isolated from soil. Int. J. Syst. Evol. Microbiol. 60, 2094-2098.
- 265 [20] Wayne, L.G., Brenner, D.J., Colwell, R.R., Grimont, P.A.D., Kandler, O., Krichevsky,
266 M.I., Moore, L.H., Moore, W.C., Murray, R.G.E. & other authors (1987) Report of the ad
267 hoc committee on reconciliation of approaches to bacterial systematics. Int. J. Syst.
268 Bacteriol. 37, 463-464.
- 269 [21] Ziemke, F., Hofle, M.G., Lalucat, J., Rosselló-Mora, R. (1998) Reclassification of
270 *Shewanella putrefaciens* Owen's genomic group II as *Shewanella baltica* sp. nov. Int. J.
271 Syst. Bacteriol. 48,179-186.
- 272
- 273

274 **Table 1.** Comparative phenotypic characteristics among 1, strain F-279,208^T; 2, *Pseudomonas*
 275 *entomophila* CECT 7985^T; 3, *Pseudomonas monteilii* BCRC 17520^T; 4, *Pseudomonas mosselii*
 276 DSM 17497^T; 5, *Pseudomonas plecoglossicida* DSM 15088^T; and 6, *Pseudomonas taiwanensis*
 277 DSM 21245^T. All data were obtained under the same conditions, except for 3 [10]. Miniaturized
 278 test results were recorded in triplicate. +, positive; -, negative; NA, not available; V, variable
 279 among trials; W, weakly positive.

Characteristic	1	2	3	4	5	6
Flagellation ^a	Single polar	Single polar	NA	Single polar	Multiple polar	One or three polar
Fluorescent pigments	+	+	+	+	-	+
King B medium (fluorescein)	+	+	-	+	_b	+
King A medium (phycocyanin)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Growth at/on						
37 °C						
45 °C	-	W	-	-	-	+
6% NaCl	+	+	+	+	-	+
Activity of enzymes (API 20NE and API 20E)						
Reduction of nitrates	-	-	-	-	+	-
Hydrolysis of gelatin	+	+	-	V	-	-
Assimilation of (API 20NE)						
L-arabinose	-	-	+	-	-	+
D-mannose	+	+	-	+	-	-
D-mannitol	+	+	-	+	-	-
N-acetyl-glucosamine	+	+	-	+	-	-
Acid from (API 20E) ^c						
D-glucose	+	+	NA	-	-	-
Enzymatic activities (API ZYM):						
Esterase C8	+	W	NA	-	+	+
Leucine arylamidase	-	+	NA	+	+	+
Carbon sources (Biolog GN2)						
Glycogen	-	-	+	W	W	-
N-acetyl-D-glucosamine	+	W	-	+	-	-
L-Arabinose	-	_d	+	_d	+	V
D-Arabitol	+	W	-	+	-	-
i-Erythritol	-	-	+	-	_d	-
D-Fructose	+	+	+	+	-	+
α-D-glucose	+	+	-	+	+	+
D-Mannitol	+	+	-	+	-	-
D-Melibiose	-	-	+	-	_d	-
β-Methyl-D-glucoside	-	-	+	-	_d	-
D-Psicose	-	-	+	W	-	W
Turanose	-	-	+	-	V	-
D-Galacturonic acid	-	-	+	-	-	+
D-Glucosaminic acid	-	-	+	-	-	-
D-Glucuronic acid	-	-	+	-	-	+
γ-Hydroxy butyric acid	-	V	-	-	-	+
p-Hydroxy phenylacetic acid	+	+	W	+	-	-
Itaconic cid	-	-	W	-	+	-
α-Keto butyric acid	-	V	-	+	W	W
D-Saccharic acid	-	+	NA	-	-	+
Glucuronamide	-	-	NA	-	-	+
D-Serine	-	_d	NA	W	+	-
Urocanic acid	+	+	NA	+	+	-
Inosine	+	+	NA	+	-	-
2-Aminoethanol	+	+	NA	-	+	+
D,L-α-Glycerol phosphate	-	W	NA	+	-	-

280 ^aFlagellation data of related *Pseudomonas* type strains was taken from Mulet et al. [10].
281 ^bReported as positive by Nishimori et al [13].
282 ^cThe color turned yellow just in the cupule indicating the acidification of the medium under
283 aerobic conditions.
284 ^dReported as positive by Mulet et al [10].
285 With the API 20NE and API 20E systems, the strain F-279,208^T was also positive for arginine
286 dihydrolase, citrate utilization, assimilation of glucose, potassium gluconate, capric acid, malic
287 acid, trisodium citrate and phenylacetic acid. The acidification of D-melibiose was variable. In
288 API ZYM system, our isolate was also positive for esterase C4, acid phosphatase and naphthol
289 AS-BI-phosphohydrolase. Activity of alkaline phosphatase and valine arylamidase were weak
290 and whereas lipase C14 was variable. In the Biolog GN2 system, strain F-279,208^T also oxidized
291 Tween 40, Tween 80, D-mannose, methyl pyruvate, mono- methyl-succinate, cis-aconitic acid,
292 citric acid, D-gluconic acid, α -keto glutaric acid, DL-lactic acid, propionic acid, quinic acid,
293 succinic acid, bromosuccinic acid, L-alaninamide, D-alanine, L-alanine, L-alanyl glycine, L-
294 asparagine, L-aspartic acid, L-glutamic acid, glycyl L-glutamic acid, L-histidine, L-histidine,
295 hydroxy-L-proline, L-leucine, L-histidine, L-ornithine, L-proline, L-pyroglutamic acid, L-
296 serine, DL-carnitine, γ -aminobutyric acid, phenylethylamine and putrescine. Acetic acid, L-
297 phenylalanine, L-threonine and glycerol were weakly oxidized. The oxidation response of
298 dextrin, formic acid, α -hydroxy butyric acid and uridine were variable. The other organic
299 substrates or enzymatic activities included in the API galleries (API 20NE, API 20E and API
300 ZYM) and Biolog GN2 microplates showed a negative result. Phenotypic proprieties of the
301 reference strains are in general accordance with results given in the literature
302

303 **Fig. 1.** Neighbour-joining trees illustrating the phylogenetic position of strain *P. soli* F-279,208^T
304 and related members of the genus *Pseudomonas* based on partial 16S rRNA (a) and
305 concatenated gene sequences (b). Bar, 0.01 expected nucleotide substitution per site.
306 *Pseudomonas fluorescens* was used as outgroup. Only bootstrap values above 50% are indicated
307 (1000 resamplings) at branchings.

a) 16S rRNA

b) MLSA

***Pseudomonas soli* sp. nov., a novel producer of xantholysin congeners**

Javier Pascual, Marina García-López, Cristina Carmona, Thiciana da S. Sousa, Nuria de Pedro, Bastien Cautain, Jesús Martín, Francisca Vicente, Fernando Reyes, Gerald F. Bills^a, Olga Genilloud*.

Fundación MEDINA, Avenida del Conocimiento, 3. Parque Tecnológico de Ciencias de la Salud. E-18016 Granada (Spain).

^aCurrent address: Texas Therapeutics Institute, The Brown Foundation Institute of Molecular Medicine, The University of Texas Health Science Center, 1881 East Road, 3SCR6.4676, Houston, TX 77054, USA.

Running title: *Pseudomonas soli* sp. nov.

*Corresponding author at: Fundación MEDINA, Avenida del Conocimiento, 3. Parque Tecnológico de Ciencias de la Salud. E-18016 Granada (Spain). Phone: + 34 958 993 965
E-mail: olga.genilloud@medinaandalucia.es

Supplementary Methods S1. Fingerprinting analysis was based on Rep PCR (GTG)₅ technique[1]. The PCR reaction mix contained 5 µl 10x buffer, 4µl MgCl₂ (25 mM), 5 µl dNTP mix (10 mM each), 5 µl DMSO, 1 µl of primer (GTG)₅ 5'-GTG GTG GTG GTGGTG-3' (50 pM), 0.5 µl Taq polymerase (5 U/µl Qbiogene), 5 µl purified DNA (50 ng/µl) in a total volume of 50 µl. The amplification protocol was 95 °C for 2 min, followed by 30 cycles of 94 °C for 2 min, 40 °C for 1 min and 65 °C for 5 min with a final extension of 65 °C for 8 min. 15 µl of each amplification product was mixed with 2 µl of a gel loading dye containing bromophenol blue and resolved in a 1.5% agarose gel in TBE buffer. Two (i) 50-2,000 bp and (ii) 125-23,100 bp ladders (Invitrogen) were used as weight size markers. The gel was electrophoresed at 90 V until the bromophenol blue marker migrated until 9 cm from the origin. The gel was stained in an ethidium bromide solution (1 mg/µl), and photographed with a digital system under UV light. To determine significant differences in the patterns, the reproducibility of results was assessed by repetition of three independent assays. The resulting image was processed with BioNumerics 6.6 software (Applied Maths). Numerical analysis of obtained patterns and dendrogram construction was calculated with Pearson correlation coefficients using UPGMA clustering method.

References

- [1] Versalovic, J., Schneider, M., de Bruijn, F.J., Lupski, J.R. (1994). Genomic fingerprinting of bacteria using repetitive sequence-based polymerase chain reaction. *Methods. Mol. Cell. Biol.* 5, 25-40

Supplementary Methods S2. Phylogenetic analyses.

Near full-length 16S rRNA gene sequence were amplified with the primer pairs FD1 (5'-AGAGTTTGATCCTGGCTCAG-3') and RP2 (5'-ACGGCTACCTTGTTACGACTT-3'). PCR mixtures were composed of 5.0 µl PCR buffer (10x), 4.0 µl MgCl₂ (25 mM), 1.0 µl dNTPs (10 mM each), 1.0 µl each forward and reverse primers (10 µM), 0.3 µl Taq polymerase (5 U/µl Qbiogene) and 5.0 µl DNA in a total volume of 50 µl. The thermal cycling program was described previously [6]. PCR products were purified and sequenced using the above primer pairs and the internal primers 926F (5'-AAACTYAAAKGAATTGACGG-3') and 1100R (5'-GGGTTGCGCTCGTTG-3') at Secugen S.L. (Madrid, Spain). The nearest phylogenetic neighbors of the isolates were determined using the EzTaxon-e database (<http://eztaxon-e.ezbiocloud.net/>) [3]. Since multilocus sequence analysis (MLSA) based on four housekeeping genes (16S rRNA, *gyrB*, *rpoB* and *rpoD*) has been established as an useful tool to more precisely determine the phylogenetic relationships among species of the genus *Pseudomonas* [5], this approach was employed here. Amplification and partial sequencing of coding genes of strain F-279,208^T were performed as described previously Ait Tayeb et al. [1] and Pascual et al. [5, 7]. The rest of the sequences analysed in this paper were obtained from public databases, and their accession numbers are displayed in the phylogenetic trees. Multiple sequence alignments were obtained using CLUSTAL_X [9] taking into account the corresponding amino acid alignments for protein-coding genes. Nucleotide sequence alignments were inspected visually to identify positions of uncertain alignment, usually at the ends of the sequences, to be corrected or omitted for further analysis. Phylogenetic relationships were analysed using the program PAUP* version 4.0b10 [8]. Neighbour-joining (NJ; with Kimura's two-parameter correction), maximum parsimony (MP; heuristic search option) and maximum likelihood (ML) analyses were computed for each of the genes separately and for the concatenated sequences. Since the lengths of the sequences used were uneven, sequences were analysed using a pairwise deletion method for gaps and missing sites, using all available comparative data from each sequence pair. For ML, the optimal models of nucleotide substitution were estimated through the program jModelTest 2.1.1 using the Akaike Information Criterion [2]. Bootstrap analyses were performed using 1000 replications for NJ and MP, and 500 replications for ML.

The four genes were checked to detect putative recombination events with the RDP4 Beta 4.16 program [4] applying the default setting except that (i) the sequences were considered lineal instead of circular, (ii) the highest acceptable p-value was 0.01, and (iii) we considered as positive those recombination events which were detected almost for two methods [6].

References

- [1] Ait Tayeb, L.A., Ageron, E., Grimont, F., Grimont, P.A. (2005) Molecular phylogeny of the genus *Pseudomonas* based on *rpoB* sequences and application for the identification of isolates. *Res. Microbiol.* 156, 763-773.
- [2] Darriba, D., Taboada, G.L., Doallo, R., Posada, D. (2012) jModelTest 2: more models, new heuristics and parallel computing. *Nature Methods* 9, 772.
- [3] Kim, O.S., Cho, Y.J., Lee, K., Yoon, S.H., Kim, M., Na, H., Park, S.C., Jeon, Y.S., Lee, J.H., Yi, H., Won, S., Chun, J. (2012) Introducing EzTaxon-e: a prokaryotic 16S rRNA Gene sequence database with phylotypes that represent uncultured species. *Int. J. Syst. Evol. Microbiol.* 62, 716-721.
- [4] Martin, D.P., Lemey, P., Lott, M., Moulton, V., Posada, D., Lefevre, P. (2010) RDP3: a flexible and fast computer program for analyzing recombination. *Bioinformatics* 26, 2462-2463.
- [5] Mulet, M., Gomila, M., Lemaitre, B., Lalucat, J., Garcia-Valdes, E. (2012) Taxonomic characterisation of *Pseudomonas* strain L48 and formal proposal of *Pseudomonas entomophila* sp. nov. *Syst. Appl. Microbiol.* 35, 145-149.
- [6] Pascual, J., Macián, M.C., Arahal, D.R., Garay, E., Pujalte, M.J. (2010) Multilocus sequence analysis of the central clade of the genus *Vibrio* by using the 16S rRNA, *recA*, *pyrH*, *rpoD*, *gyrB*, *rctB* and *toxR* genes. *Int. J. Syst. Evol. Microbiol.* 60, 154-165.
- [7] Pascual, J., Lucena T., Ruvira, M.A., Giordano, A., Gambacorta, A., Garay, E., Arahal, D.R., Pujalte, M.J., Macián, M.C. (2011) *Pseudomonas litoralis* sp. nov., isolated from Mediterranean seawater. *Int. J. Syst. Evol. Microbiol.* 62, 438-444.
- [8] Swofford, D.L. (2002) PAUP*. Phylogenetic Analysis Using Parsimony (*and other methods). Version 4.0b10 (Sinauer Associates: Sunderland, MA).
- [9] Thompson, J.D., Gibson, T.J., Plewniak, F., Jeanmougin, F., Higgins, D.G. (1997) The CLUSTAL_X windows interface: Flexible strategies for multiple sequence alignment aided by quality analysis tools. *Nucleic. Acids Res.* 25, 4876-4882.

Supplementary Methods S3. Isolation of xantholysin A.

A 1L broth of strain F-279,208^T grown in Kido medium (glycerol 2%, sodium L-glutamate monohydrate 1%, yeast extract 0.25%, pH adjusted to 7.0) for three days on an orbital shaker (220 rpm) at 18 °C was acidified with HCl 6N to pH 3. The acidified broth was extracted with methylethylketone (MEK, 1l) with shaking at 220 rpm for 1 h. The aqueous phase was then separated by centrifugation and discarded, and the organic phase (ca. 1l) was concentrated to dryness on a rotary evaporator. The dried extract was fractionated by reversed-phase preparative HPLC (Agilent Zorbax SB-C8, 21.2 x 250 mm, 7 μm; 20ml/min, UV detection at 210 nm, gradient H₂O + 0.1% TFA:CH₃CN + 0.1% TFA from 5% to 100% organic in 40 minutes) yielding a fraction eluting at 23.0 min that was further purified by semipreparative HPLC (Agilent Zorbax RX-C8, 9.4 x 250 mm, 5μm; 3.6 ml/min, UV detection at 210 nm, gradient H₂O + 0.1% TFA:CH₃CN + 0.1% TFA from 70% to 90% organic in 40 minutes) to yield 2.0 mg of xantholysin A [1] as a white amorphous solid.

References

- [1] Li W., Rokni-Zadeh H., De Vleeschouwer M., Ghequire M.G., Sinnaeve D., Xie G.L., Rozenski J., Madder A., Martins J.C., De Mot R. (2013). The antimicrobial compound xantholysin defines a new group of *Pseudomonas* cyclic lipopeptides. PLoS One 8:e62946.

Supplementary Methods S4. Human cell lines culture and cytotoxicity assays.

Human cell lines used in this study were: hepatocellular carcinoma HePG2, human pancreas epithelial cell MiaPaca-2, and human breast adenocarcinoma from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC, Manassas, VA) and human Renal Cell Carcinoma Cell line RCC4 (ECACC, UK) stably transfected with an empty vector, pcDNA3 (ECACC N-03112702; called RCC4-VA) conferring neomycin resistance, or with pcDNA3-VHL (ECACC N-0312703; called RCC4-VHL) conferring neomycin resistance and encoding the VHL tumor suppressor gene product pVHL. The original renal carcinoma cell line RCC4 is VHL-deficient.

To evaluate the cytotoxicity of the purified compounds, the MTT (3-(4,5-Dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide) test was performed. This is a colorimetric assay for measuring the activity of cellular enzymes that reduce the tetrazolium dye, MTT, to its insoluble formazan, giving a purple color. This assay measures mitochondrial metabolic activity via NAD(P)H-dependent cellular oxidoreductase enzymes and may, under defined conditions, reflect the number of viable cells. The automated screening process was formatted in 96-well plates (Greiner Bio-One, Frickenhausen, Germany), and workflow was automated. Cells were seeded at a density of 20,000 cells per well using a multidrop dispenser (MTX Lab Systems, Inc. Vienna, VA, USA). Cells were, incubated at 37 °C in 5 % CO₂ using 96 wells microplates (BD Falcon), after 24 hours, the medium was replaced and controls (8 mM methyl methanesulfonate) and extracts were added to the plates. Then the plates were incubated at 37 °C in 5 % CO₂ incubator for 24 hour more before adding the MTT solution for 3 hours at 37 °C in 5% CO₂ incubator. The supernatant was removed and 100 µl of DMSO 100% was added. The plates were gently shaken to solubilize the formed formazan. The absorbance was measured using a VictorTM multireader at a wavelength of 570 nm.

Supplementary Table S1. Cellular FAMES content of *Pseudomonas soli* sp. nov. F-279,208^T and the type strains of closely *Pseudomonas* species. All data from this study except for 3 (Wang et al., 2010). Strains were cultured on TSA at 28°C for 24h. Values are percentages of total fatty acids. –, not detectable; tr, trace amount (< 1%).

Strains: 1, strain F-279,208^T; 2, *Pseudomonas entomophila* CECT 7985^T; 3, *Pseudomonas monteilii* BCRC 17520^T; 4, *Pseudomonas mosselii* DSM 17497^T; 5, *Pseudomonas plecoglossicida* DSM 15088^T; and 6, *Pseudomonas taiwanensis* DSM 21245^T.

Fatty acid	1	2	3	4	5	6
C _{10:0} 3-OH	12.4	5.0	3.6	6.1	10.6	15.8
C _{12:0}	1.6	4.7	3.2	5.2	3.3	3.7
C _{12:0} 2-OH	6.6	5.4	2.9	8.6	8.3	10.2
C _{12:1} 3-OH	1.9	tr	tr	tr	2.2	1.6
C _{12:0} 3-OH	5.4	5.0	4.0	6.1	5.7	6.1
C _{14:0}	tr	tr	tr	tr	tr	tr
C _{16:0}	23.7	23.5	18.9	16.1	17.3	19.1
C _{17:0} CYCLO	7.2	1.2	tr	2.3	4.9	9.0
C _{18:1} ω 7c	14.4	25.4	31.6	24.0	11.3	10.7
C _{18:0}	tr	tr	1.1	tr	tr	tr
Summed feature 3 ^a	24.8	28.4	32.4	29.2	35.2	21.7
Summed unknown fatty acids	tr	tr	-	tr	tr	tr

^a Summed feature represents a set of more than one fatty acid that could not be resolved by GLC with the MIDI system. Summed feature 2 contained C_{14:0} 3-OH and/or C_{16:1} ISO I; Summed feature 3 contained C_{16:1} ω 7c and/or C_{15:0} ISO 2-OH

References

- [1] Wang, L.T., Tai, C.J., Wu, Y.C., Chen, Y.B., Lee, F.L., Wang, S.L. (2010) *Pseudomonas taiwanensis* sp. nov., isolated from soil. Int. J. Syst. Evol. Microbiol. 60, 2094-2098.

Supplementary Table S2. 16S rRNA, *rpoB*, *rpoD*, *gyrB* and concatenated genes pairwise sequence similarity between strains *P. soli* F-279,208^T and the type strains of the *Pseudomonas* spp. belonging to the *P. putida* group.

Species	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
16S rRNA											
1- <i>P. soli</i> F-279,208 ^T											
2- <i>P. cremoricolorata</i>	98.0										
3- <i>P. entomophila</i>	99.2	98.4									
4- <i>P. fulva</i>	98.4	97.8	98.3								
5- <i>P. japonica</i>	98.1	98.5	98.5	97.5							
6- <i>P. monteilii</i>	99.0	98.5	99.7	98.4	98.6						
7- <i>P. mosselii</i>	99.5	98.4	99.7	98.2	98.5	99.5					
8- <i>P. parafulva</i>	99.0	98.3	98.7	99.4	98.0	99.0	98.7				
9- <i>P. plecoglossicida</i>	99.1	98.6	99.6	98.3	98.7	99.8	99.4	99.0			
10- <i>P. putida</i>	98.3	98.8	98.7	98.2	98.5	98.8	98.6	98.7	98.9		
11- <i>P. taiwanensis</i>	99.2	98.6	99.6	98.5	98.7	99.9	99.6	99.1	99.9	98.9	
12- <i>P. vranovensis</i>	97.6	98.0	97.9	97.1	98.3	98.1	97.9	97.6	98.1	98.7	98.2
<i>rpoB</i>											
1- <i>P. soli</i> F-279,208 ^T											
2- <i>P. cremoricolorata</i>	94.2										
3- <i>P. entomophila</i>	93.8	92.0									
4- <i>P. fulva</i>	94.4	99.6	92.5								
5- <i>P. japonica</i>	93.4	91.5	93.8	91.9							
6- <i>P. monteilii</i>	94.3	93.0	92.9	93.0	92.7						
7- <i>P. mosselii</i>	96.1	94.5	94.3	94.8	94.3	95.6					
8- <i>P. parafulva</i>	94.0	93.9	92.7	94.3	92.3	94.2	94.6				
9- <i>P. plecoglossicida</i>	95.0	94.0	93.2	94.0	92.2	96.0	95.8	95.0			
10- <i>P. putida</i>	94.9	93.9	93.6	94.1	93.1	96.4	96.0	95.2	96.5		
11- <i>P. taiwanensis</i>	93.8	91.8	94.3	92.0	93.0	94.7	94.4	93.1	94.3	94.4	
12- <i>P. vranovensis</i>	90.9	90.4	93.3	90.8	93.6	91.7	91.8	91.7	91.5	91.9	91.7
<i>rpoD</i>											
1- <i>P. soli</i> F-279,208 ^T											
2- <i>P. cremoricolorata</i>	81.9										
3- <i>P. entomophila</i>	89.1	83.7									
4- <i>P. fulva</i>	83.3	82.3	84.4								
5- <i>P. japonica</i>	78.4	79.0	79.8	79.0							
6- <i>P. monteilii</i>	85.6	81.3	85.6	90.0	79.4						
7- <i>P. mosselii</i>	91.6	83.7	91.5	84.5	78.3	87.0					
8- <i>P. parafulva</i>	83.7	83.5	83.5	89.0	78.7	88.6	84.8				
9- <i>P. plecoglossicida</i>	87.1	82.1	89.8	87.5	79.5	89.8	88.2	86.9			
10- <i>P. putida</i>	85.3	82.3	85.4	89.5	79.4	92.4	86.6	89.2	88.0		
11- <i>P. taiwanensis</i>	85.8	81.6	85.6	85.7	78.1	86.5	87.9	86.0	89.6	86.9	
12- <i>P. vranovensis</i>	79.8	76.5	78.4	76.7	79.2	78.2	80.3	77.9	77.7	77.3	77.9

Species	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
gyrB											
1- <i>P. soli</i> F-279,208 ^T											
2- <i>P. cremoricolorata</i>	87.0										
3- <i>P. entomophila</i>	93.8	87.9									
4- <i>P. fulva</i>	86.1	87.2	86.8								
5- <i>P. japonica</i>	88.1	85.8	88.2	85.1							
6- <i>P. monteilii</i>	89.5	88.3	91.5	88.1	87.7						
7- <i>P. mosselii</i>	93.5	88.1	95.8	87.1	89.4	92.1					
8- <i>P. parafulva</i>	88.0	87.3	89.3	87.4	85.4	89.0	88.3				
9- <i>P. plecoglossicida</i>	91.7	87.1	91.7	86.2	86.8	91.4	92.1	88.0			
10- <i>P. putida</i>	89.5	88.7	90.3	87.9	86.7	92.7	90.3	89.8	89.3		
11- <i>P. taiwanensis</i>	88.4	86.2	89.0	85.5	87.4	88.7	89.3	85.7	88.4	88.7	
12- <i>P. vranovensis</i>	87.2	86.2	87.9	84.5	88.7	87.2	87.4	87.2	88.4	88.2	86.5
Concatenated genes											
1- <i>P. soli</i> F-279,208 ^T											
2- <i>P. cremoricolorata</i>	92.0										
3- <i>P. entomophila</i>	95.0	92.1									
4- <i>P. fulva</i>	92.3	93.3	92.1								
5- <i>P. japonica</i>	91.4	90.7	91.9	90.3							
6- <i>P. monteilii</i>	93.6	92.0	93.8	93.6	91.5						
7- <i>P. mosselii</i>	96.1	92.8	96.1	92.7	91.9	94.8					
8- <i>P. parafulva</i>	92.8	92.4	92.6	94.0	90.7	94.0	93.2				
9- <i>P. plecoglossicida</i>	94.4	92.2	94.7	93.0	91.3	95.4	95.1	93.7			
10- <i>P. putida</i>	93.4	92.6	93.3	93.6	91.4	95.9	94.1	94.4	94.4		
11- <i>P. taiwanensis</i>	93.3	91.4	93.7	92.0	91.3	93.9	94.2	92.6	94.4	93.6	
12- <i>P. vranovensis</i>	90.7	89.9	91.2	89.4	91.8	90.7	91.1	90.5	90.8	91.0	90.5

Supplementary Table S3. IC₅₀ of xantholysin A, B and D against several human tumor cell lines (μM)^a. Both curves (RCC-VHL and RCC-VA) are represented in the Supplementary Fig. 8.

Compound ID	Liver	Pancreas	Breast	Kidney HIF Pathway	
	HepG2	MiaPaca_2	MCF7	RCC_VA	RCC_VHL
Xantholysin A	>50	>50	>50	17.9	>50
Xantholysin B	>50	>50	>50	>50	>50
Xantholysin D	>50	>50	>50	>50	>50

^a50 μM is the highest concentration tested in this study because at higher concentration compounds in general are considerate inactive. 50 μM can be considered as a high concentration referred to already described compounds in this pathway but it is not the case for a hit discovered in a primary screening and before chemical modifications. Furthermore activity must be compared to toxicity and in this case the toxicity is very low.

Supplementary Fig. S1. Phase-contrast image showing morphology and single polar flagellum of *P. soli* sp. nov. F-279.208^T grown under optimum conditions and after staining; bar. 1 μ m.

Supplementary Fig. S2. Colonies of *P. soli* sp. nov. F-279.208^T grown on TSA at 28 °C for 48h. (a) whole plate; (b) close-up. showing stellate precipitates in the culture medium.

Supplementary Fig. S3. (a) Rep PCR (GTG)₅ fingerprints. M1.125- 23.100 bp DNA molecular size marker; M2. 50-2.000 bp DNA molecular size marker; 1. *P. soli* F-279.208^T; 2. *P. mosselii* DSM 17497^T; 3. *P. entomophila* CECT 7985^T; 4. *P. plecoglossicida* DSM 15088^T; 5. *P. taiwanensis* DSM 21245^T. (b) Dendrogram generated by the UPGMA method and Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient.

Supplementary Fig. S4. Neighbour-joining trees illustrating the phylogenetic position of strain *P. soli* F-279.208^T and related members of the genus *Pseudomonas* based on *rpoB* (a), *rpoD* (b) and *gyrB* (d) gene sequences (e). Bar. 0.01 expected nucleotide substitution per site. *Pseudomonas fluorescens* was used as outgroup. Only bootstrap values above 50% are indicated (1000 resamplings) at branches.

a) *rpoB*

b) *rpoD*

c) *gyrB*

0.01

Supplementary Fig. S5. Maximum parsimony trees illustrating the phylogenetic positions of strain *P. soli* F-279.208^T and related members of the genus *Pseudomonas* based on partial 16S rRNA (a). *rpoB* (b). *rpoD* (c). *gyrB* (d) and concatenated gene sequences (e). Bar. 20 estimated substitution per 100 bases positions. *Pseudomonas fluorescens* was used as outgroup. Only bootstrap values above 50% are indicated (1000 resamplings) at branches.

a) 16S rRNA

b) *rpoB*

c) *rpoD*

d) *gyrB*

e) MLSA

Supplementary Fig. S6. Maximum likelihood trees illustrating the phylogenetic position of strain *P. soli* F-279.208^T and related members of the genus *Pseudomonas* based on 16S rRNA (a). *rpoB* (b). *rpoD* (c). *gyrB* (d) and concatenated gene sequences (e). Bar. 0.01 expected nucleotide substitution per site. *Pseudomonas fluorescens* was used as outgroup. Only bootstrap values above 50% are indicated (500 resamplings) at branches.

a) 16S rRNA

b) *rpoB*

c) *rpoD*

H
0.01

d) *gyrB*

H
0.01

e) MLSA

H
0.01

Supplementary Fig. S7. Chromatographic separation of xantholysin congeners. A) LC-UV-HRMS chromatogram of extracted fermentation prior to purification. B) HPLC-UV trace of pure xantholysin A and C) HRMS of pure xantholysin A.

A)

B)

C)

Supplementary Fig. S8. Dose-response curves of xantholysin A treatment of RCC4 transfected cells with vector alone (RCC4-VA) or with expressing vector for VHL (RCC4-VHL) to rescue the inactivated function of VHL in RCC4 normal cells. The raw data point (4 points) for each concentration and cell line is shown.

